

Fuzzy random forests: A new approach to groundwater contaminant modelling in Uganda

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Summary

Geogenic groundwater contamination challenges universal access to safe drinking water. Understanding distributions of groundwater quality is important to identify hazards but a lack of data and appropriate modelling techniques hampers efforts. Here we use a modified random forest (fuzzy random forest) supported by recent water quality data to predict the spatial distribution of likely groundwater manganese exceedance and measures of prediction (un)certainty across Uganda. Relatively high certainty (< 1 % variation) of threshold exceedance (> 95 % probability) is identified across Southwest and North Uganda, highlighting locations to consider for appropriately-selected remediation and/or further monitoring for improved quality of groundwater derived drinking sources.

KEYWORDS: pollutants, manganese, machine learning, sustainable development goals

1. Introduction

Groundwater is a critical resource, key to achieving universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water (SDG 6). However, groundwater contamination from anthropogenic and geogenic sources can lead to varied public health consequences (UN, 2022). Groundwater contamination is a concern across Sub-Saharan Africa, where many people rely on unimproved groundwater resources for drinking (UN, 2022). In Uganda, three-quarters of the population rely on groundwater which may be impacted by geogenic contaminants including manganese and fluoride (IGRAC, 2025).

To better assess risk and consider potential remediation requirements, distributions of groundwater quality are highly informative (Podgorski et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2021). In Uganda, recent groundwater chemistry surveillance (BGS, 2020; Muloogi et al., 2026; Namatovu et al., 2023; Wilson et al., 2024), facilitates the use of machine learning (ML) to predict groundwater quality that was previously hampered by insufficient data (Richards et al., 2023). However, ML approaches can be restricted in the information they provide about uncertainty, limiting how much information is available for groundwater decision making (Dennis et al., 2026a).

Fuzzy approaches are recognised to effectively represent classification uncertainty but uptake is limited by the arbitrary selection of class membership functions (Huck et al., 2023). Huck et al., (2023) provide an empirical alternative to membership definition, facilitating method uptake. Dennis et al. (2026) generalise the approach to landscape classification and combine fuzzy membership definition with Monte Carlo simulation to generate many possible landscape classification surfaces. Variation between classification surfaces can be used to provide information on prediction uncertainty and the surfaces can be used in subsequent analysis to propagate uncertainties.

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Here we predict manganese groundwater contamination across Uganda using a fuzzy random forest (FRF) classifier and estimate the proportion of the population living in affected areas. We present the results as maps and distributions, demonstrating how increased information can be made available for groundwater management-related decision making.

2. Methods

2.1 Study area

Uganda has a growing population of over 45 million (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2024). The country has plentiful surface water resources (**Figure 1**), yet over 75 % of the population rely on groundwater (MWE, 2023). Factors potentially impacting groundwater quality include geogenic pollutants, agricultural intensification and poor sanitation practices (Muloogi et al., 2026; Wilson et al., 2024).

Figure 1 Locations of Uganda groundwater chemistry data used in this study (BGS, 2020; Muloogi et al., 2026; Namatovu et al., 2023; Wilson et al., 2024).

2.2 Groundwater chemistry

Here we focus on manganese, of which excessive consumption can cause neurological complications. As such, 0.08 mg/L is recommended as a drinking water limit (WHO, 2024). Groundwater manganese concentrations (n=324) across Uganda were collated (BGS, 2020; Muloogi et al., 2026; Namatovu et al., 2023; Wilson et al., 2024) (**Figure 1**) and converted into a binary variable (> 0.08 mg/L = 1, otherwise 0).

2.3 Predictor variables

Datasets (n=54) representing environmental parameters with groundwater chemistry relationships were downloaded (Amatulli et al., 2020; ESA, 2021; Fan et al., 2013; Hengl, 2018; Hengl et al., 2017; Pelletier et al., 2016; Trabucco and Zomer, 2019; Yamazaki et al., 2019). All datasets were tested for multicollinearity and refined using reported geostatistical relationships to manganese (Podgorski et al., 2022). Variable importance analysis was performed and parameters with < 20% contribution to prediction were removed, leaving 12 predictor variables (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Final predictor variables and their relative model prediction contribution.

2.4 Fuzzy random forest

Fuzzy random forest (FRF) is a modified random forest classifier, where individual decision tree predictions are modified using the overall classifier confusion matrix and combined using the Power-Posterior method to form per-cell Beta distributions of probable contaminant exceedance above drinking water limits (Dennis et al., 2026b). FRF was implemented in Python 3.13 and the model was trained with 80 % of the training data and evaluated using a confusion matrix and area under the receiving operator curve (AUC) score calculated with the remaining 20 %.

Monte Carlo simulation was then used to randomly draw from the Beta distributions and generate 1000 landscapes predicting the probability of manganese exceedance in groundwater across Uganda. The mean probability of contaminant limit exceedance was calculated, with variance around the mean providing information about prediction uncertainty. Using each landscape, the proportion of the population living in areas of threshold exceeded above 95 % probability was calculated by intersecting

the landscape with Meta's High Resolution Population Density Map (CIESIN, 2022). Using the drawn values ($n=1000$) a distribution was built and descriptive statistics (median, absolute deviation) calculated.

3. Results

The spatial distribution of probable groundwater manganese exceedance across Uganda is shown (Figure 3). The model had an AUC of 0.80, indicating good model prediction performance (0.5 = random prediction, 1 = perfect prediction). Higher probable exceedances were predicted in the south-west, surrounding Mbarara City and extending northwest to Fort Portal and northeast to the capital Kampala. Higher probabilities were also predicted in the north-west, to the north of Gulu, and in the east, just south of Mbale City.

Figure 3 FRF predicted probability of groundwater manganese above 0.08 mg/L.

The intersection of probable exceedance with population density revealed a median of 25.9 % of the Ugandan population (i.e. ~ 11.6 million people) live in areas of high probability (> 95 %) manganese exceedance (**Figure 4**). Deviation around the median was low (± 0.2 %) suggesting high classification certainty. Regional comparison revealed that the Western region had the highest predicted proportion of its population living in high probability threshold exceedance areas (40.8 ± 0.4 %; ~ 3.7 million people), whilst the Eastern region has the lowest (10.6 ± 0.3 % = $\sim 810,000$ people). Deviation around the median was low (< 1 %) for all regions but was lowest in the East (0.3 %) and highest in the North (0.6 %). Our results appear to be dependent on the inclusion of the overall classifier confusion matrix to modify probabilities, and the impact of its inclusion on outputs is an area of ongoing investigation.

Figure 4 Proportion of total Ugandan population (grey) and of population within each region living in areas with high probability (> 95 %) groundwater manganese exceeding 0.08 mg/L.

4. Discussion and conclusions

Understanding groundwater chemistry distribution is important to improving universal access to safe drinking water. In countries such as Uganda where more comprehensive water quality data are expanding, opportunities to apply ML to better characterise groundwater quality are growing.

Here, we implemented a modified random forest (Dennis et al., 2026a, 2026b) to map probable groundwater manganese exceedance across Uganda. Preliminary predictions suggest high proportions (> 40%) of the Western Ugandan population may live in probable manganese hazard areas, highlighting where groundwater remediation activities may be required (noting comprehensive water quality analysis should be used to inform remediation decisions), increase information regarding access to safer drinking water sources, and reduce possible associated public health impacts. Using the FRF approach, information on variability in predicted exceedance was made available, providing useful uncertainty insights. Variation in predicted proportions of the population living in areas of high probability (> 95 %) manganese exceedance was low (< 1 %), suggesting high certainty in predictions. Ongoing work will focus on understanding the role of the confusion matrix in model results, the modelling of other contaminants (notably arsenic, fluoride, iron, coliforms) and the integration of cost analyses of selected remediation approaches into the method.

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6. Reproducibility Statement

Groundwater data sources are as cited. A working example of the FRF method based on UK land cover data and implemented in Python 3.13 is available at: <https://github.com/jonnyhuck/fuzzy-random-forest>.

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Biographies

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